

Microwave assisted synthesis of 2,3,4-trisubstituted 1,2-dihydropyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole

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Abstract : A new methodology for the synthesis of 2,3,4-trisubstituted 1,2-dihydropyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole has been described. All the synthesized compounds were characterized on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR and elemental analyses. Synthesized compounds exhibited moderate to good anti-fungal and anti-bacterial activities.

Keywords : 2-Aminobenzimidazole, microwave-assisted synthesis, pyrimidobenzimidazoles.

Introduction

Various benzimidazole derivatives are of special interest because of their diverse pharmaceutical activities like antihistaminic¹, anesthetic², antipyretic² and anti-tumor³. Here, we report the synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives using domestic microwave, which resulted in the dramatic increase in yield of chemical transformations, cleaner products compared with conventional heating⁴.

Antibacterial activity :

The synthesized compounds (3a-e) have been evaluated for their biological activities by agar diffusion medium at 250 ppm against the *S. aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*-2510 using standard antibiotic *Streptomycin* sulphate and dimethyl formamide as a control of the solvent. Plates were incubated 48 h at 30 °C and the zones of inhibition were measured in mm have been incorporated in Table 3. All synthesized compounds were found to be moderately active against both types of bacteria.

Antifungal activity :

Similarly, the compounds were also tested for their fungicidal activities against *Aspergillus niger*-MTCC-2255 and *Penicillium chrysogenum*-NCIM-723 using Greseofulvin as a control. By careful scrutiny of the results it is revealed that the series of 2,3,4-trisubstituted 1,2-dihydropyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole (3a-e) exhibited spectacular anti-fungal activities against test organism *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*.

Results and discussion

The reaction of 2-aminobenzimidazole with β-aryl-α-cynoacrylonitrile derivatives 2a-e in presence of catalytic amount of TEA in an open glass container and the reaction mixture irradiated in a microwave oven for 30–40 s with intermittent irradiation to afford in 70% yield of 3a-e. In the classical approach⁴, this cyclocondensation reaction requires longer reaction time. In addition, this method suffers from tedious and time-consuming work-ups. In contrast, under microwave irradiation, the reactions are completed within only 30–40 s and afforded good yields of the products⁵. By using domestic microwave oven method, the reaction is also possible for 20 mmol scale. The products were characterized on the basis of their IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopic data.

In the same way equimolar amount of 2-aminobenzimidazole with ethyl β-(substituted phenyl)-α-cynoacrylates 4a-e was mixed in an open glass container and irradiated under microwave oven for 30 s with intermittent irradiation afforded about 90% yields of 5a-e. Comparative results with respect to time and yield have been incorporated in Table 1. In the IR spectrum 5a-e showed the absence of the ester carbonyl absorption band and the presence of amide band in the region 1697 cm⁻¹. The elemental analyses data have been incorporated in Table 2. Antimicrobial screening results of compounds 3a-e are shown in Table 3.

Table 1. Yields and reaction time used for the microwave assisted synthesis^a

Entry	Microwave method		Conventional method	
	Reaction time (s)	Yield (%)	Reaction time (min)	Yield ^d (%)
3a	30	70	5	45
3b	30	45	5	30
3c	30	60	5	37
3d	40	45	5	37
3e	40	50	5	35
5a	30	80	5	50
5b	30	78	5	45
5c	30	90	5	60
5d	30	80	5	65
5e	30	70	5	40

Table 2. Analytical data for compounds 3a-e and 5a-e

Entry	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)		
		C	H	N
3a	207	71.07	4.56	24.37
		(71.19)	(4.60)	(24.35)
3b	215	68.13	4.76	22.07
		(68.11)	(4.70)	(22.35)
3c	238	63.46	3.76	21.76
		(63.42)	(3.75)	(21.77)
3d	215	61.44	3.64	25.28
		(71.19)	(3.60)	(25.29)
3e	240	67.32	4.32	23.09
		(67.30)	(4.30)	(23.10)
5a	295	71.32	3.52	19.57
		(71.31)	(3.50)	(19.56)
5b	240	68.35	3.82	17.71
		(68.35)	(3.81)	(17.70)
5c	245	63.66	2.83	17.47
		(63.65)	(3.82)	(17.46)
5d	270	61.63	2.74	21.14
		(61.64)	(2.25)	(21.13)
5e	290	67.55	3.33	18.53
		(71.19)	(3.30)	(18.52)

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded using KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum on FTIR spectrometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Jeol-JMSD-300 spectrophotometer. Microwave irradiations were conducted in a domestic microwave oven [Samsung M197DN (2450 MHz, 1500 W)].

The starting material 2-amino benzimidazole are commonly synthesized by reacting *o*-phenylenediamine with guanidine⁶.

General procedure :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, nitriles (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30–60 s. The progress of reaction was monitored on TLC using benzene : ethyl acetate (90 : 10) as the eluent. The compound was cooled and recrystallised in ethanol to get the desired product.

4-Amino-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydropyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (**3a**) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β-phenyl-α-cyanoacrylonitrile (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.400 g; m.p. 207 °C (Ref.⁴ : 205–207 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 1650 (C=N), 3319 (NH), 2227 (CN) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.0–8.6 (10H, m, Ar-H), 9.8 (2H, br, s, NH₂), 8.3 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-Amino-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (**3b**) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β-(4-methoxyphenyl)-α-cyanoacrylonitrile (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.285 g; m.p. 215 °C (Ref.⁴ 212–213 °C) IR (KBr) : ν 1590 (C=N), 3350 (N-H), 2171 (CN) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 6.9–7.9 (9H, m, Ar-H), 9.8 (2H, br, s, NH₂), 2.5 (3H, s, OCH₃), 8.1 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-Amino-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimido-[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (**3c**) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β-(4-chlorophenyl)-α-cyanoacrylonitrile (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.386 g; m.p. 238 °C (Ref.⁴ : 232 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 1598 (C=N), 3355 (N-H), 2222 (CN) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.1–8.1 (9H, m, Ar-H), 10.0 (2H, br, s, NH₂), 8.1 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-Amino-2-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimido-[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (**3d**) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β-(3-nitrophenyl)-

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities of compounds **3a-e**

Compd.	R	(Zone of inhibition in mm)			
		Bacteria		Fungi	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>
3a	H	-	20	26	18
3b	-OCH ₃	-	15	17	20
3c	-Cl	5	28	28	34
3d	NO ₂	8	21	31	24
3e	-OH	-	15	24	22
<i>Streptomycin</i>		23	34	-	-
Sulphate					
Flucanazole		-	-	30	30
DMF		-	-	-	-

R' = (a) H, (b) *p*-OCH₃, (c) *p*-Cl, (d) *m*-NO₂, (e) *o*-OH

Scheme 1

α -cyanoacrylonitrile (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 40 s. Yield : 0.298 g; m.p. 215 °C (Ref.⁴ : 216–217 °C); IR (KBr) : ν 1625 (C=N), 3360 (N-H), 2260 (CN) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.2–7.7 (9H, m, Ar-H), 11.5 (2H, br, s, NH₂), 7.9 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-Amino-2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimido[1,2-a]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (3e) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β -(2-hydroxyphenyl)- α -cyanoacrylonitrile (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open

glass container and irradiated with microwave for 40 s. Yield : 0.303 g; m.p. 240 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 1637 (C=N), 3335 (N-H), 3300 (O-H), 2212 (CN) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 6.67–7.46 (8H, m, Ar-H), 11.7 (2H, br, s, NH₂), 5.4 (1H, s, -OH), 8.03 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-Phenyl-2-pyrimidone[1,2-a]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (5a) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β -phenyl- α -cyanoacrylate (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.457 g; m.p. 295 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 1697 (C=O), 3305

(N-H), 2205 (CN) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ 6.9–8.2 (9H, m, Ar-H), 10.6 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-pyrimidone[1,2-a]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (5b) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β -(4-methoxyphenyl)- α -cyanoacrylate (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.492 g; m.p. 240 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : ν 1697 (C=O), 3305 (N-H), 2205 (CN) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.26–7.56 (8H, m, Ar-H), 9.52 (1H, s, NH), 3.55 (3H, s, OCH_3) ppm.

4-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-pyrimidone[1,2-a]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (5c) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β -(4-chlorophenyl)- α -cyanoacrylate (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.576 g; m.p. 245 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : ν 1678 (C=O), 3325 (N-H), 2188 (CN) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.46–7.67 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.63 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-(3-Nitrophenyl)-2-pyrimidone[1,2-a]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (5d) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β -(3-nitrophenyl)- α -cyanoacrylate (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.529 g; m.p. 270 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : ν 1703 (C=O), 3348 (N-H), 2260 (CN) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.0–8.0 (8H, m, Ar-H), 10.0 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

4-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-2-pyrimidone[1,2-a]benzimidazole-3-carbonitrile (5e) :

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2 mmol) **1**, β -(2-hydroxyphenyl)-

α -cyanoacrylate (2 mmol) and catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) in ethanol were taken into a open glass container and irradiated with microwave for 30 s. Yield : 0.422 g; m.p. 290 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : ν 1697 (C=O), 3303 (N-H), 3250 (O-H), 2205 (CN) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ 7.15–7.62 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.6 (1H, s, -OH), 9.7 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

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